

Airports as art-space

The results of researches on the use of airports as distinctive culturological platforms (art spaces) are presented. Illustration of features of the formation and functioning of the Art Space of Terminal D International Airport Boryspil (Kiev).

Aviation occupies not only a special place in the transport system of countries and the world, but also has an important impact on society in general.

The emergence and development of aviation is the result of the work of a large number of scientists and specialists in the aviation and space industry, military and civil aviation.

The first flight of aircrafts (PV) turned into amazing spectacular events. Further development of aviation is also accompanied by demonstration flights of new types of aircrafts within international aviation and space salons, in particular Paris Air Show Le Bourget, since 1908, International Exhibition of General Aviation (France Air Expo Lyon), since 1910. These events have turned into real air shows which are attended by thousands of fans and guests (fig.1).

a

b

Fig.1. Posters:

a - Semaine d'Aviation de Lyon. 1910. Charles Tichon;

b - The People's Aviation Meet, 3rd International, Los Angeles, January 20-28, 1912. Dominguez Field

Airports don't stay aloof too. Worldwide practice has many examples of the transformation of airports into real museums of fine and monumental arts. First of all, this is Denver International Airport, where the frescoes of the Mexican monumental artist Leo Tangumi are located on four walls. At the entrance to the airport there is a 10-meter sculpture of the Blue Mustang of Luis Jimenez, which symbolizes "The Wild Spirit of the Old American West".

Facades of air terminals at national airports are decorated with sculptural compositions (for example Terminal 1, Lviv), the interiors are decorated with mosaic panels (Terminal B, Boryspil; Chernivtsi), sculptural portraits of statesmen (Terminal B, Boryspil, demonstrations during reconstruction) etc. At the station square are sculptures of political figures (Donetsk, sculptures dismantled over time), decorative flowerbeds (Borispol, they were dismantled during the reconstruction) etc.

In front of the facade of the International Airport (IA) "Kyiv / Zhuliany" in 2015 an An-24 was installed, which continues the most common placement practice at the station square for airports of the former USSR as witnesses of certain historical events.

Lately, airports are increasingly gaining signs of cities and turning into enterprises, which provide services not only for aviation purposes. It significantly changes the concept of the development of modern airports. Railway station areas are decorated not only by memorable signs, sculptural compositions, fountains, decorative flowerbeds. Landscape parks (Hamad International Airport, Mauritius International Airport), children's and sports grounds (International Simferopol Airport); multi-level parking lots (Houston George Bush Intercontinental Airport); transport-transfer nodes (Lyon Saint Exupery Airport); office and cultural centers, hotels (Munich Airport); high-rise dominant building of bizarre forms appear, whose function is executed by Airfield Traffic Control Tower (Vienna International Airport, Baku Heydar Aliyev Airport).

Such practice is extended by both Ukrainian metropolitan airports.

In 2015, an An-24 plane was turned into an art object on the Kyiv-Zhulyany airport landing site (Fig. 2). It is planned to open the gallery in the cabin of plane until 2020.

Fig.2. Art-object, railway station square, Kyiv / "Zhulyany" IA, artist Avtandil Gurgenzidze [1]

The introduction in 2012 of operation of the terminal D of the Boryspil Aircraft Company provided an opportunity to use it as a kind of culturological platform. This takes into account the psychological factor: different categories of passengers are differently interested and enjoy additional services. Therefore, the main emphasis is on the passengers of departure, transit and transfer, who have free time to participate in the spectacular events held in departure hall.

In the departure hall there is an open-loft zone "I LOVE KBP", accompanied by various thematic concerts with the appropriate decoration of the premises, etc. For example, on the eve of the New 2019 Terminal D was decorated with the figure of St. Nicholas, who controls the harness of planes.

The waiting room, more than 800 m long, turned into an exhibition hall with a throughput of 3 thousand viewers (passengers) for an hour. This is an impressive figure that can be envied by the world's cultural and entertainment institutions!

Among the first events of 2015 is the opening of the Gallery of National Pride, which, according to the organizers of the airport and Artyana Art Foundation, was supposed to become an artistic trademark of the country, to promote the Ukrainian culture and identify the airport as a significant Ukrainian space. At the opening of the art space were presented original 44 paintings of Maria Prymachenko, People's Artist of Ukraine (1988), Laureate of the Taras Shevchenko`s National Prize of Ukraine (1960) (Fig. 3, a).

Significant for Ukrainians and guests of the country was the opening in 2016 of an exhibition devoted to the memory of the Heroes of Heavenly Hundreds. More than 50 photos, made by correspondents who worked on the Maidan, formed the exposition "Revolution of Dignity. The future is made by free people "(Fig. 3, b).

Fig. 3. Fragments of entertainment establishments, Boryspil Airlines:

a - exhibitions of works by Maria Prymachenko, 2015 [2];

b - Exposition "Revolution of Dignity. The future is made by free people ", 2016 [3]

Another important event for the country is the exhibition of photographs "Projection" devoted to the heroes of the anti-terrorist operation (ATO) - "real people with real emotions and feelings" (Fig. 4).

a

b

Fig.4. Fragments of the exhibition "Projection", "Boryspil" IA, July 2017, photo by G. Agieieva

It is necessary to mention events that had an "aviation orientation":

- Exhibition of collections of photos from Air France Airlines «Stars between heaven and earth, 1955-1971» on which world-class personalities such as Brigitte Bardot, Frank Sinatra, Marlene Dietrich, Alfred Hitchcock, Federico Fellini, Yves Saint Laurent, Sean Connery, Charles Aznavour and others are represented [4];
- An exhibition of posters from the series "100 Famous Ukrainians", prepared by illustrators of the Pictoric Club (July 2015). The exhibition's share is devoted to the designers of aviation equipment and rocket-space systems, in particular, Igor Sikorsky (Fig. 5, a) and Sergey Korolev (Fig. 5, b);
- The final of the "Sky Swallow" contest for the best form of flight attendants of the railways - partners of the "Boryspil", 2017, 2018 years [5].

a

b

Fig. 5. Fragments of the exhibition of posters of the series "100 Famous Ukrainians", July 2015, photo by G. Agieieva

The international airport "Boryspil" annually accepts millions of visitors from different countries of the world. This is not just a multi-kilometer zone, separated from a large city, where aircraft are serviced. It is a living mechanism by which we need to communicate with the rest of the world. And it is the art space that actively spreads on the territory of the airport, contributes to this.

This is a kind of space, where the first impressions of Ukraine are created in the first moments of stay on its land.

It is an enormous mechanism by which it is possible to convey the soul of the Ukrainian people by means of art which are accessible to everyone and do not require special interpretation and translation.

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